

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Sellors**FIRST NAME:** Joanne**PROGRAM CODE:** DMCR**COURSE CODE:** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** ONE**INSTRUCTOR:** Gulma**Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: Word

List your 5 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Essay writing (EUCLID 2021, 1-12)
2. Punctuation (EUCLID 2021, 15-22)
3. American v British English (EUCLID 2021, 25-27)
4. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 33-39)
5. Latin (EUCLID 2021, 58-62)

INTRODUCTION TO ACADEMIC WRITING

1) WRITING AN ESSAY

It has been several years since I have written a paper at this level. The biggest change in this is the permitted use of computer software that is designed to help and edit for you. But at the basic level, the process and the requirements have remained the same. I was reminded that essays still have the same basic format and that they have the same structure, with the most important tip being, “Do not lose track of the question or task” (EUCLID 2021, 11).

I understand that it is supplied and recommended by EUCLID, but I admit to finding it a bit uncomfortable. I am old school enough to remember when using a new thing called a hand-held calculator on a college-level math exam was considered cheating. These new software programs look wonderful, and I am sure that eventually I will learn to love them, and they will become second nature.

When I read through the outline, I found the reminders of the basics very helpful. I will do my best to “stay focused,” “write clearly,” and try “not to be boring” and not to feel like a fool when I stand there “reading my work out loud” (EUCLID 2021, 13).

I was one of the people who were taught in High School to write in the first person, but I will do my best to adapt to the recommended format.

2) PUNCTUATION

I believe that this is the section that I learned the most from. I have seen so many of the examples over the years but never took the time to understand them and generally just read past them. The most interesting and helpful was about the use of “square brackets” (EUCLID 2021, 17). I never knew what they were other than an extraneous key on my laptop. The most interesting thing that I found was finally an explanation of the use of “Colon and Semicolon,” this is something that I have been struggling with for years. I am sure that when I take the time and concerted effort to use them correctly, it will greatly improve my writing style and reach (EUCLID 2021, 18).

I am sure that getting used to the use of these newfound tools will be a challenge, but I can see where the use of the above-mentioned software will be a plus.

3) AMERICAN V BRITISH ENGLISH

I am an American by birth, and American English is my first language, but my mother is British. I spent many summers visiting my extended family in Yorkshire with my many cousins and learning British English. While it has been several years since I was there, we have maintained contact, and I think I have retained most of what I learned. It is still good enough that I could translate Monty Phyton and Benny Hill to my children when they started watching them. Also, when my husband was on a business trip to London, I was able to translate the menu and the snack items for him (EUCLID 2021, 26).

While this has been interesting and helpful, information was the section on spelling and pronunciation (EUCLID 2021, 25). Due to a learning disability (Dysgraphia), I have always been a very poor speller. I never realized that I had been mixing my spelling between American and British English all my life.

Again, I will refer to the software and the translation feature I never knew Word had.

4) PLAGIRISUM AND CITING

This is where the Zotero program will be a beneficial tool. Compared to the tools I have been using on Word, this will be easier to reference but will be a great encouragement to expand my work.

I also understand that it will be a fine line between citing and letting the program write my work for me. I can see that the guidance on “In-Text” should help me overcome my concerns over the Zotero software (EUCLID 2021, 35). I grade High School tests for

an American Home School company, and we are already having a problem with the students using software and AI to do the bulk of the writing for them.

I already tend to overdo my writing. I will have to keep reminding myself that less is more. Just because it is easy to do does not mean I should.

5) LATIN

I have been in Law for over thirty years. Latin is heavily used in Law. Until reading the Course pack, I knew the scope (EUCLID 2021, 59). I find I have a new interest in citing them. I am looking forward to becoming fluent in their use. But as mentioned above, less is more. With Latin's two thousand-plus years of history, it is prevalent in most writing and cultures. This is something that I am looking forward to practicing using it without sounding pretentious. I never realized the varieties and variations that are used.

6) CONCLUSION

As I said in my introduction, it has been several years since I have written at this level, and I never had access to the software that is now taken for granted. In this brief exercise, I have realized how rusty my skills are and how out of date my knowledge of the current software programs is. While I was a little frustrated with the fact that with five degrees on my resume, I had to take a writing course, I am very glad that I am taking this, and I look forward to your feedback.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui: Euclid University.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.